

An Optimal Solution for Balanced and Unbalanced Assignment Problems under Crisp and Trapezoidal Fuzzy Numbers Using Row Minimum Allocation Method

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Abstract

In this paper, to solving an Balanced and Unbalanced Assignment Problem. This process involves providing an IBFS optimality. I introduce the Row Minimum Allocation Method (RMAM) in order to maintain an optimum balanced and unbalanced assignment problems. To less reductions and steps we get the optimum. The proposed algorithms are clear to understand and easy to access when it comes to discussing the trapezoidal fuzzy number balanced and unbalanced assignment problems in real life situations.

Keywords :

Balanced Assignment Problem(BAP), Unbalanced Assignment Problem (UBAP), Row Minimum Allocation Method (RMAM), Trapezoidal Fuzzy Number (TrpFN):

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Introduction

An assignment problem is a special case of transportation problem where the aim is to assign a wealth of resources to an equal variety of activities in possible to minimize planned costs or significantly increase total profits from assignments. The challenge of assignment occurs to originate as available resources, such as employees, highways, factories, areas, etc., have varying degrees of applicability in pursuing development projects. The real problem, instead, is how to build the assignments to maximize the given objective. One of the specific combinatorial optimization problems in the management branch or computational modeling in mathematics is the problem of availability. Dantzig.G.B, Thapa.M.N[1], the assignment method is a special linear programming technique to solve these problems, along with other choosing the right man for the right job for more than Every choice is possible and every single individual can still do jobs. The main objective is to allocate a number of events at minimal cost (or full profit) or some other unique purpose to an incredible number of facilities. Hungarian mathematician Konig (1931) developed the Hungarian assignment method which provides us with an efficient way to obtain the optimal solution without achieving a comparable evaluation on each solution. It depends on the premise that the given cost variable is transformed to a virtual world of opportunity costs. The assignment method presented above involves the number of columns and rows in the assignment matrix to always be equal. However, R.K.Gupta, [2],Kanti, Swarup, P.K, Gupta[3], the assignment problem is called an unbalanced problem if the given cost matrix is not a square matrix. From such cases the matrix needs to add a dummy row(s) or column(s) to make it a square matrix (with zeros as cost elements). Mukherjee, S., and Basu, K.[5], describe an application-fuzzy ranking system for solving Fuzzy Cost assignment problems.Venkatachalapathy M, Nagarajan P and Jayaraja A.[6,7], to apply row penalty method for applying unbalanced assignment problems and triangular fuzzy and trapezoidal fuzzy numbers.

Mathematical Formulation:

Let number of rows = m and number of columns = n . If $m = n$ then an Assignment Problem(AP) is said to be Balanced Assignment Problem(BAP) otherwise it is said to be Unbalanced Assignment Problem (UBAP).

Case 1: If $m < n$ then mathematically the UBAP can be stated as follows

According to 'n' resources (or facilities) and 'n' activities (or jobs) and efficiency (in terms of potential costs, benefits, time, etc.) of each resource (facility) for each activity (job), the problem lies in allocating the

resource to one and only one activity (job) in order to make sure optimum job satisfaction level. The objective function is to,

$$\text{Minimize } Z = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{C}_{ij} x_{ij}$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = 1, \text{ for all } i \text{ (Resource Availability)}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} = 0 \text{ or } 1, \text{ for all } j \text{ (Activity Requirements)}$$

$$\text{Where } x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & , \text{ if } i^{\text{th}} \text{ machine is assigned to the } j^{\text{th}} \text{ job} \\ 0 & , \text{ if } i^{\text{th}} \text{ machine is not assigned to the } j^{\text{th}} \text{ job} \end{cases}$$

Case 2: If $m > n$ then mathematically the UBAP can be stated as follows:

$$\text{Minimize } Z = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{C}_{ij} x_{ij}$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = 0 \text{ or } 1, \text{ for all } i \text{ (Resource Availability)}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} = 1, \text{ for all } j \text{ (Activity Requirements)}$$

$$\text{Where } x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & , \text{ if } i^{\text{th}} \text{ machine is assigned to the } j^{\text{th}} \text{ job} \\ 0 & , \text{ if } i^{\text{th}} \text{ machine is not assigned to the } j^{\text{th}} \text{ job} \end{cases}$$

Definition: Trapezoidal Fuzzy Number:

A fuzzy set \tilde{A} , defined on the universal set of real numbers \mathfrak{R} , is said to be generalized trapezoidal fuzzy numbers if its membership function has the following characteristics:

1. $\mu_{\tilde{A}} : \mathfrak{R} \rightarrow [0, \omega]$ is continuous.
2. $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = 0$ for all $x \in (-\infty, a] \cup [d, \infty)$.
3. $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x)$ Strictly increasing on $[a, b]$ and strictly decreasing on $[c, d]$.
4. $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \omega$, for all $x \in [b, c]$, where $0 < \omega \leq 1$.

Arithmetic Operations:

The arithmetic operations of two generalized trapezoidal fuzzy numbers, defined on the universal set of real numbers \mathfrak{R} , are presented. If $\tilde{A}_1 = (k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4; \omega_1)$ and $\tilde{A}_2 = (l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4; \omega_2)$ be two generalized trapezoidal fuzzy numbers then

- (i) $\tilde{A}_1 + \tilde{A}_2 = (k_1 + l_1, k_2 + l_2, k_3 + l_3, k_4 + l_4; \text{minimum}(\omega_1, \omega_2))$
- (ii) $\tilde{A}_1 - \tilde{A}_2 = (k_1 - l_4, k_2 - l_3, k_3 - l_2, k_4 - l_1; \text{minimum}(\omega_1, \omega_2))$

Ranking function

An efficient approach for comparing the fuzzy numbers is by the use of ranking function, $\mathfrak{R} : F(\mathfrak{R}) \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$, where $F(\mathfrak{R})$ is a set of fuzzy numbers defined on the set of real numbers, which maps each fuzzy number into the real line, where a natural order exists i.e.,

- (i) $\tilde{A} >_{\mathfrak{R}} \tilde{B}$ if and only if $\mathfrak{R}(\tilde{A}) > \mathfrak{R}(\tilde{B})$
- (ii) $\tilde{A} <_{\mathfrak{R}} \tilde{B}$ if and only if $\mathfrak{R}(\tilde{A}) < \mathfrak{R}(\tilde{B})$
- (iii) $\tilde{A} =_{\mathfrak{R}} \tilde{B}$ if and only if $\mathfrak{R}(\tilde{A}) = \mathfrak{R}(\tilde{B})$

Let $\tilde{A}_1 = (k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4; \omega_1)$ and $\tilde{A}_2 = (l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4; \omega_2)$ be two generalized trapezoidal fuzzy numbers and $\omega = \text{minimum}(\omega_1, \omega_2)$ then $\Re(\tilde{A}) = \frac{\omega(k_1 + k_2 + k_3 + k_4)}{4}$ and $\Re(\tilde{B}) = \frac{\omega(l_1 + l_2 + l_3 + l_4)}{4}$.

Row Minimum Allocations Method (RMAM) Algorithms for Balanced & Unbalanced (Crisp & Trapezoidal Fuzzy) Assignment Problems:

- Step 1:** Construct the data matrix of the assignment problem. Consider row as a worker (resource) and column as a job (activity).
- Step 2:** To find minimum unit cost for each row, whichever minimum value is available in the respective row, select it and write it in term of activities under row. Continue this process for all the rows and write in term of row as a worker (resource) and column as a job (activity).
- Step 3:** Let for each resource if there is unique (tie) activity then assigned that activity for the corresponding resource, hence we achieved our optimal solution.
- Step 4:** If tie occurs choose arbitrarily to find the minimum and next minimum unit cost for all those rows which have same activity. Assign that activity which has minimum values. Delete those rows and corresponding columns for which those resources have been assigned.
- Step 5:** Repeat steps 4 to 5 till all jobs are assigned uniquely to the Corresponding activity.
- Step 6:** Once all the jobs are assigned then calculate the total cost by using the expression.

Applications of the Approach method Numerical Example:

Problem 1: Balanced Assignment Problem

A batch of five jobs I, II, III, IV, V can be assigned to five different machines A, B, C, D, E. The set up time in hours for each job on various machines is given. Find an optimal assignment of jobs to minimize the total set up time.

Table 1 .Matrix Entries Represent the Jobs and Machines

	I	II	III	IV	V
A	100	90	60	80	120
B	70	90	110	85	105
C	130	110	120	125	140
D	100	120	90	105	85
E	120	140	135	100	115

To select the row minimum values

A	III	60
B	I	70
C	II	110
D	V	85
E	IV	100

Table 2: Optimum Allocation Entries in Row Minimum Allocation Method

	I	II	III	IV	V
A	100	90	60	80	120
B	70	90	110	85	105
C	130	110	120	125	140
D	100	120	90	105	85
E	120	140	135	100	115

The optimum job schedule is allocate the machines are

$$A \rightarrow III, B \rightarrow I, C \rightarrow II, D \rightarrow V, E \rightarrow IV$$

The optimal solution of balanced assignment problems is =60+70+110+85+100
= 425 hours.

Problem 2. Obtain Unbalanced Assignment Problem using RMAM:

Table 3 .Matrix Entries Represent the Processing Time in Hours

	M1	M2	M3	M4
J1	18	24	28	32
J2	8	13	17	19
J3	10	15	19	22

Solution:

The problem given is unbalanced problem of converting balanced assignment problem and introducing dummy row.

Table 4 .Modified Matrix Entries Represent the Processing Time in Hours

	M1	M2	M3	M4
J1	18	24	28	32
J2	8	13	17	19
J3	10	15	19	22
J4	0	0	0	0

New method for Row Minimum Allocation Method of assignment problem, we get the optimal solution. By solving unbalanced assignment problem to obtain the optimal assignment total set up time and schedule as follows. The optimum job schedule is allocate the machines are

To select the row minimum values

J1	M1	18
J2	M2	13
J3	M3	19
J4	M4	0

$$J_1 \rightarrow M_1, J_2 \rightarrow M_2, J_3 \rightarrow M_3, J_4 \rightarrow \text{No Job} .$$

The optimal solution of unbalanced assignment problems is =18+13+19+0
=50 hours.

Problem 1: Row Minimum Allocation Method for Trapezoidal Fuzzy Balanced Assignment Problem:

Our Row Minimum Allocation Method is solving for unbalanced assignment problem is applicable. It is required for add dummy row/column .

Table 5:Matrix Entries Represent the Processing Time (in Hours) Trapezoidal Fuzzy Numbers

	I	II	III	IV	V
A	(100,150,250,300;0.5)	(80,130,220,290;0.5)	(60,70,170,180;0.5)	(80,110,210,240;0.5)	(140,190,290,340;0.5)
B	(80,90,190,200;0.5)	(80,130,220,290;0.5)	(120,170,270,320;0.5)	(90,120,220,250;0.5)	(110,160,260,310;0.5)
C	(150,210,310,370;0.5)	(120,170,270,320;0.5)	(140,190,290,340;0.5)	(150,200,300,350;0.5)	(180,230,330,380;0.5)
D	(100,150,250,300;0.5)	(140,190,290,340;0.5)	(80,130,220,290;0.5)	(110,160,260,310;0.5)	(90,120,220,250;0.5)
E	(140,190,290,340;0.5)	(180,230,330,380;0.5)	(160,210,310,360;0.5)	(100,150,250,300;0.5)	(130,180,280,330;0.5)

To select the row minimum values

A	III	(60,70,170,180;0.5)
B	I	(80,90,190,200;0.5)
C	II	(120,170,270,320;0.5)
D	V	(90,120,220,250;0.5)
E	IV	(100,150,250,300;0.5)

Table 6:Optimum Allocation Entries in Row Minimum Allocation Method

	I	II	III	IV	V
A	(100,150,250,300;0.5)	(80,130,220,290;0.5)	(60,70,170,180;0.5)	(80,110,210,240;0.5)	(140,190,290,340;0.5)
B	(80,90,190,200;0.5)	(80,130,220,290;0.5)	(120,170,270,320;0.5)	(90,120,220,250;0.5)	(110,160,260,310;0.5)
C	(150,210,310,370;0.5)	(120,170,270,320;0.5)	(140,190,290,340;0.5)	(150,200,300,350;0.5)	(180,230,330,380;0.5)
D	(100,150,250,300;0.5)	(140,190,290,340;0.5)	(80,130,220,290;0.5)	(110,160,260,310;0.5)	(90,120,220,250;0.5)
E	(140,190,290,340;0.5)	(180,230,330,380;0.5)	(160,210,310,360;0.5)	(100,150,250,300;0.5)	(130,180,280,330;0.5)

The optimum job schedule is allocate the machines are

$$A \rightarrow III, B \rightarrow I, C \rightarrow I, D \rightarrow V, E \rightarrow IV$$

The optimal solution of balanced assignment problems is

$$\begin{aligned}
&=(60,70,170,180:0.5)+(80,90,190,200:0.5)+(120,170,270,320:0.5)+(90,120,220,250:0.5)+(100,150,250,300:0.5) \\
&=(450,600,1100,1250;0.5) \\
&= 425 \text{ hours.}
\end{aligned}$$

Problem 2: Obtain Row Minimum Allocation Method for Trapezoidal Fuzzy Unbalanced Assignment Problem:

Our Row Minimum Allocation Method is solving for unbalanced assignment problem is applicable. It is required for add dummy row/column .

Table 7: Matrix Entries Represent the Processing Time (in Hours) Trapezoidal Fuzzy Numbers

	A	B	C	D
J1	(26,31,41,46:0.5)	(38,43,53,58:0.5)	(46,51,61,66:0.5)	(54,59,69,74:0.5)
J2	(6,11,21,26:0.5)	(16,21,31,36:0.5)	(26,29,39,44:0.5)	(28,33,43,48:0.5)
J3	(10,15,25,30:0.5)	(20,25,35,40:0.5)	(28,33,43,48:0.5)	(34,39,49,54:0.5)

Table 6: Balanced Trapezoidal Fuzzy Assignment table

	M1	M2	M3	M4
J1	(26,31,41,46:0.5)	(38,43,53,58:0.5)	(46,51,61,66:0.5)	(54,59,69,74:0.5)
J2	(6,11,21,26:0.5)	(16,21,31,36:0.5)	(26,29,39,44:0.5)	(28,33,43,48:0.5)
J3	(10,15,25,30:0.5)	(20,25,35,40:0.5)	(28,33,43,48:0.5)	(34,39,49,54:0.5)
J4	(0,0,0,0:1)	(0,0,0,0:1)	(0,0,0,0:1)	(0,0,0,0:1)

The minimum values is used to classify the first rows, then join the row to determine the total table value. Supposing cost is tie means objectively crossed. After identifying the table's minimum cost simultaneously eliminate the concern row and column. Repeat the apply the final value to both the process.

To select the row minimum values

J1	M1	(26,31,41,46:0.5)
J2	M2	(16,21,31,36:0.5)
J3	M3	(28,33,43,48:0.5)
J4	M4	(0,0,0,0:1)

The optimum job schedule is allocate the machines are $J_1 \rightarrow M_1, J_2 \rightarrow M_2, J_3 \rightarrow M_3, No Job \rightarrow M_4$

The optimal solution of unbalanced trapezoidel fuzzy assignment problems using ranking function is

$$\begin{aligned}
&=(26,31,41,46:0.5)+ (16,21,31,36:0.5)+ (28,33,43,48:0.5) \\
&= (50,75,125,150:0.5)
\end{aligned}$$

$$R(A)=50 \text{ hours}$$

Results and Discussion:

Table 8: Comparision table for Hungarian Method and Row Minimum Allocation Method

Numerical Examples	Crisp Values for Hungarian method[1,2,3]	Trapezoidal Fuzzy Number Using Ranking function for Hungarian method[1,2,3]	Row Minimum Allocation Method for crisp values	Row Minimum Allocation Method for Trapezoidel Fuzzy Number Using Ranking function
1	50	R(A)= (50,75,125,150:0.5) =50	50	R(A)=(50,75,125,150:0.5) =50
2	425	R(A)=(450,600,1100,1250;0.5) =425	425	R(A)=(450,600,1100,1250;0.5) =425

Conclusion

In this paper, the problem for balanced and unbalanced assignment is considered to be an imprecise number explained by numbers with trapezoidel fuzzy which are more feasible and general throughout nature. We have formulated row minimum allocation methods assignment problems and minimizing everything respectively. By our Row Minimum Allocation Method then the minimum number reduction to easily and acknowledged the optimal solution for any problems without changing the order of assigning less reductions and computations. Our algorithms are easy to understand and easy to apply whenever it comes to identifying the fuzzy balanced and unbalanced assignment problems that occur in real life situations.

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